

Interpretable Clustering Using Dempster-Shafer Theory

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Abstract: This study presents DSclustering, a novel algorithm that merges clustering validity with interpretability using the Dempster-Shafer theory. Traditional clustering methods like K-means, DBSCAN, and agglomerative clustering, while widely used for their efficiency and accuracy, often fall short in transparency, creating barriers in critical fields such as healthcare, finance, and consumer analytics where decision-making requires clear, interpretable insights. DSclustering aims to bridge this gap by assigning clusters based on belief functions from Dempster-Shafer theory, which allows it to generate rule-based explanations for each data point's cluster assignment. Through detailed experiments on real-world datasets, including consumer behavior and airline satisfaction data, we evaluate DSclustering against traditional algorithms using key metrics such as Silhouette score, Rand index and Dunn's index for clustering validity. The results indicate that DSclustering not only performs competitively but also offers a clear interpretative layer, making it suitable for applications where understanding model outputs is as essential as the accuracy of the outputs themselves. This work underscores the increasing importance of interpretability in machine learning, particularly in unsupervised learning, where transparency is typically challenging to achieve. DSclustering demonstrates a promising approach for balancing robust clustering with user-oriented interpretability, potentially encouraging broader adoption of interpretable clustering models in data-critical industries.

Keywords: Clustering, Interpretability, Dempster-Shafer, Machine Learning, Unsupervised Learning

Categories: H.3.1, H.3.2, H.3.3, H.3.7, H.5.1

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1 Introduction

The exponential growth in data generation across various domains has led to the development of predictive models, particularly within data science, to infer unknown characteristics of samples based on observed attributes. Supervised learning encompasses techniques such as classification and regression, which predict categorical and continuous outcomes, respectively. In contrast, unsupervised learning methods, such as clustering, focus on identifying patterns and grouping similar data points without predefined labels [Zeng, 24].

Model evaluation typically prioritizes the assessment of accuracy, which measures the degree of alignment between predicted outcomes and actual values. In classification models, performance metrics such as accuracy, sensitivity, the area under the ROC curve, and the F1 score are commonly employed [Tharwat, 21]. Clustering models, however, do not have explicit ground truths for comparison, shifting the emphasis to validity metrics like Dunn's index [Dunn, 74], the Silhouette score [Shahapure, 20], and the Rand index [Warrens, 20].

In recent years, increasing emphasis has been placed on developing machine-learning models that not only deliver high accuracy but also are interpretable. Interpretability refers to the capability of a model to provide human-understandable explanations for its predictions or groupings. Despite its critical role, there is no universally accepted definition or standardized method for measuring interpretability. Nonetheless, researchers concur that interpretability is vital for deriving meaningful insights from data and understanding the underlying phenomena [Lipton, 16], [Rudin, 19].

The ideal data science model would achieve both high performance and interpretability. However, this balance often proves elusive, as complex, high-performance models—such as gradient boosting and random forests—are typically regarded as "black-box" systems due to their opaque decision-making processes [Li, 20]. Conversely, simpler models like linear regression and decision trees are inherently more interpretable [Gilpin, 19], yet they are often limited by their inability to handle non-linear relationships or overly complex structures.

In [Peñafiel, 20] authors introduced a novel classifier, the Dempster-Shafer classifier (DSGD), based on Dempster-Shafer theory (DST) [Shafer, 76]. This model demonstrates accuracy comparable to black-box models while providing clear, understandable rules for its predictions, thereby achieving a balance between performance and interpretability.

The need for clustering methods that effectively combine high validity and interpretability has become increasingly apparent. A promising research avenue involves the development of algorithms capable of producing results comparable to popular clustering techniques—such as k-means, DBSCAN, and agglomerative clustering—while maintaining interpretability. Such advancements could enhance user confidence by providing greater transparency in the clustering process [Hu, 24].

The proposed research aims to address this challenge by designing a clustering algorithm that integrates validity and interpretability in a unique and balanced manner. Unlike current interpretable clustering algorithms, which often compromise validity, the proposed method aims to retain robust validity while offering straightforward rules for understanding cluster formation. Additionally, the algorithm incorporates a novel

measure of uncertainty for each cluster assignment, further enhancing trust and insight into the results.

The methodology begins with a conventional clustering step, assigning each data point to a cluster. Depending on user preferences, the algorithm selects the optimal clustering solution based on either the highest Silhouette score or the most frequent cluster assignment for individual instances. Subsequently, each cluster is treated as a class, and an interpretable classifier, specifically the DSGD, is trained on this labelled data. This approach generates explicit rules that describe the formation of clusters.

This research contributes to the field of data science by presenting a novel clustering framework that integrates the reliability of established clustering techniques with the interpretability of the DSGD method. By combining these attributes, the approach offers a transparent and effective solution to clustering, addressing the growing demand for tools that are both valid and interpretable.

The idea was presented for the first time in a short paper [Valdivia, 24] in a very general way and without any formal testing of it. In this paper, we formally describe the methodology and present the results of tests performed in order to demonstrate the validity of this approach.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews related work on interpretable clustering, including prototype-based, rule-based, and self-explaining models. Section 3 details the proposed methodology, introducing DSClustering and its underlying components. Section 4 presents experimental results, evaluating both clustering validity and interpretability. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper with a discussion of the findings, limitations, and future research directions.

2 Related Work

Interpretable clustering refers to the process of organizing data points into clusters or groups where humans can easily understand both the clustering process and the results. Unlike traditional clustering methods (e.g., K-means or DBSCAN [Zhang, 17]) that may produce clusters without clear interpretation, interpretable clustering aims to provide clusters that are meaningful and explainable, through either simple rules or transparent models. Interpretability matters in clustering because in many real-world applications, such as healthcare or finance, it is not enough for a model to simply group data. Decision-makers need to understand why certain data points are grouped together. They also need to trust the clustering model's outputs in order to take actionable insights based on the model's results. Interpretable clustering ensures that users can explain the groupings to stakeholders, and that the clustering outcomes are transparent and consistent with domain knowledge [Gavrilova, 24].

2.1 Prototype-based Clustering

Prototype-based clustering refers to those models which are based on identifying representative data points (prototypes) from each cluster that summarize the characteristics of the cluster. K-Medoids [Park, 09] clustering is generally considered a prototype-based interpretable clustering method. It is similar to K-means in that it partitions data into clusters based on similarity, but instead of using centroids, it selects actual data points (medoids) as cluster centers. This makes K-Medoids clustering more

robust to noise and outliers, as medoids are real data points and not just mathematical averages. The interpretability of K-Medoids stems from these medoids, which represent central, exemplary points within each cluster, making it easier for users to understand what each cluster represents by examining these representative points. Unlike methods that rely on centroids or averages that might not correspond to any actual data point, the use of real data points as medoids enhances the interpretability of K-Medoids clustering, especially in applications where it is essential to have representative examples of clusters. Another example of prototype-based clustering is K-means clustering. Like K-Medoids, K-means aims to partition the dataset into clusters by assigning each data point to the nearest cluster center, known as the centroid. However, unlike K-Medoids, K-means uses the average of the points within each cluster as the centroid, which can sometimes lead to reduced robustness in the presence of outliers. Prototype-based clustering methods, including K-means and K-Medoids, are widely used due to their efficiency and interpretability, particularly in applications where understanding a "central" representation of each cluster is beneficial.

2.2 Rule-based Clustering

Rule-based clustering is a type of clustering that generates interpretable rules to define cluster boundaries, focusing on creating logical, human-understandable rules rather than just numerical criteria. These methods are particularly useful in domains where transparency and interpretability are critical, such as healthcare, finance, and customer segmentation. Rule-based clustering typically uses decision trees or association rules to form clusters that are easy for users to understand, interpret, and apply in decision-making [Bertsimas, 21]. Rule-based clustering methods provide interpretable structures, such as "if-then" rules, that explain how data points are assigned to specific clusters. This is different from distance-based clustering (like K-means) or density-based clustering (like DBSCAN), which rely on numerical thresholds or proximity measures that are harder to interpret directly. By producing human-readable rules, rule-based clustering enables users to understand the logic behind each cluster, making it ideal for applications requiring model transparency. Rule-based clustering offers highly interpretable clusters, as users can directly see the conditions that define each cluster. These methods can handle a wide variety of data types, including categorical and continuous features, by creating flexible and understandable rules. In high-stakes industries, rule-based clustering provides transparency, enabling stakeholders to trust the clustering process and make decisions based on easily understood criteria.

Decision trees are frequently used for rule-based clustering due to their inherent structure, which partitions the dataset into clusters (or classes) based on a series of if-then conditions. CART (Classification and Regression Trees) [Loh, 11] and C4.5 [Ruggieri,02] algorithms can be adapted to form clusters by grouping data points at each leaf node. Each path from the root node to a leaf in a decision tree represents a set of rules that define a particular cluster. MODL (Minimum Optimal Description Length) [Boullé,06] clustering is a Bayesian approach that uses rule-based criteria to define clusters. It creates interpretable rules by balancing cluster compactness and simplicity, aiming to produce the most informative and parsimonious set of clusters. RIPPER [Cohen, 95] (Repeated Incremental Pruning to Produce Error Reduction) is a rule-learning algorithm primarily used for classification but can be adapted for clustering by

creating sets of rules that define clusters based on data attributes. It iteratively refines these rules to ensure that each cluster is distinct and well-defined.

2.3 Self-explaining Clustering

Self-explaining clustering models are a type of clustering approach that inherently provide interpretability by design. Unlike traditional clustering methods, which often require post-hoc explanations or auxiliary models to clarify their results, self-explaining clustering models are constructed to generate clusters with interpretable, human-understandable characteristics. These models aim to ensure that the reasoning behind cluster formation is clear and can be directly derived from the clustering process itself. The characteristics of these kind of models are intrinsic interpretability. These models are designed to be transparent in their clustering process, making it possible for users to understand why each data point is assigned to a specific cluster without needing additional tools or explanations.

Many self-explaining clustering models use rules or conditions, such as “if-then” statements, to define each cluster. This rule-based structure enables users to see the decision criteria used to group data points.

Self-explaining models often align clustering decisions with domain-specific knowledge, ensuring that the clusters are both meaningful and interpretable within a given context. Some examples are Decision Tree-Based Clustering. Decision trees can be adapted to perform clustering, where each leaf node represents a cluster. The path to each leaf node represents a set of conditions (rules) that define the cluster, making it easy for users to understand the logic behind each cluster.

Hierarchical clustering, particularly agglomerative clustering, can be adapted into a self-explaining model by labelling clusters at each level with interpretable group characteristics. This approach provides a hierarchical breakdown of data, where each split is defined by interpretable criteria, allowing users to understand the entire clustering hierarchy.

Rule-Based Clustering, such as RUC, uses association rules derived from the data to define clusters. This approach is inherently interpretable since each cluster is associated with clear, rule-based definitions that specify which features or combinations of features qualify data points for the cluster.

Self-Explaining Clustering Models is that they exhibit Enhanced Transparency because they provide immediate insights into why clusters are formed, making the model more transparent and trustworthy, and they do not make use of additional tools, since these models produce interpretable results directly; therefore, they eliminate the need for post-hoc interpretability methods or additional tools, simplifying the clustering workflow.

According to the performed literature review, we can identify three open issues in interpretable clustering: The first one is that there is a trade-off between interpretability and accuracy that is highly interpretable models (like decision trees) may sacrifice clustering performance. This has been also identified for other supervised AI models for classification and regression. Another identified issue is the scalability of some of the interpretable methods like rule-based clustering, which may not scale well to large datasets. Finally, a still open issue remains the subjectivity in interpretation; there is still no agreement about an objective measurement of interpretability. What is

interpretable for one user may not be for another; hence, interpretability depends on context and domain knowledge.

3 Methodology

In this section, we first provide a subsection with a brief description of the DST, which is the basis for the DSGD classifier which will be explained in the next subchapter, Finally, we provide an explanation of the DS clustering algorithm, which is the new model proposed in this work.

3.1 Overview of the Dempster-Shafer Theory and Its Relevance

The DST of plausibility has significantly influenced the development of explainable AI (XAI) models, particularly in the areas of uncertainty representation, decision-making, and reasoning under incomplete or imprecise information. Unlike probabilistic models, which require precise probabilities, the DST framework uses belief functions and plausibility functions to represent degrees of belief about hypotheses. This allows XAI systems to handle situations where evidence is ambiguous or incomplete. Therefore, it provides a clear explanation of how confidence levels are computed from evidence, making it easier to communicate uncertainty to end users in a comprehensible way.

DST is built around two key mathematical constructs: *belief functions* and *plausibility functions*, both of which operate on subsets of a universal set, known as the frame of discernment (Θ). The frame of discernment represents all possible outcomes of a problem, and its subsets, called focal elements, represent specific hypotheses.

A basic probability assignment (BPA) function, denoted as $m: 2\Theta \rightarrow [0, 1]$, is the cornerstone of the theory. It assigns a value $m(A)$ to each subset $A \subseteq \Theta$, where $m(A)$ represents the portion of evidence supporting exactly A , without endorsing any of its subsets. The sum of BPAs across all subsets satisfies $\sum_{A \subseteq \Theta} m(A) = 1$, and $m(\emptyset) = 0$. In the DST mass assignment functions are provided by experts. As a simple example, we can consider a physician assessing the risk of an individual of having a heart attack based only on the level of cholesterol measured. The 2 possible outcomes are high or low risk of having a stroke denoted by A and B respectively. The physician may assess that if the level exceeds 250, then the mass for having high risk is 0.3, the mass for low risk is 0.2 and the uncertainty is 0.5. This is represented in table 1. Note that if there would be more than 2 outcomes the table of BPA would grow exponentially.

BPA for individuals having cholesterol level > 250	
Mass for outcome A (high)	0.3
Mass for outcome B (low)	0.2
Uncertainty (A or B)	0.5

Table 1: Example of mass assignment for assessing the possibility of having a heart attack based on the fact of having a cholesterol level > 250

From the BPA, two important measures are derived:

1. Belief (*Bel*): This quantifies the total evidence that supports a subset *A* directly and through its subsets. Mathematically, this is defined in formula (1):

$$Bel(A) = \sum_{B \subseteq A} m(B) \tag{1}$$

2. Plausibility (*Pl*): This measures the extent to which *A* is not contradicted by the evidence. It includes all subsets of Θ that intersect with *A*, as shown in formula (2):

$$Pl(A) = \sum_{B \cap A \neq \emptyset} m(B) \tag{2}$$

Belief and plausibility are related through $P(A)=1-Bel(A^c)$, where A^c is the complement of *A*. This defines a range $[Bel(A),Pl(A)]$, which captures the uncertainty about *A*. In our example of table 1, we can calculate $Bel(A) = 0.3$ and $Pl(A) = 0.8$ while $Bel(B) = 0.2$ and $Pl(B) = 0.7$.

A crucial aspect of the theory is Dempster’s Rule of Combination, which merges evidence from two independent sources. For two BPAs, m_1 and m_2 , the combined BPA is given by formula (3):

$$m(A) = \frac{\sum_{B \cap C = A \neq \emptyset} m_1(B) \cdot m_2(C)}{1 - K} \tag{3}$$

Where *K* is a normalization factor accounting for conflicting evidence, as shown in formula (4):

$$K = \sum_{B \cap C \neq \emptyset} m_1(B) \cdot m_2(C) \tag{4}$$

This rule allows for the fusion of evidence while discounting conflict. These mathematical elements enable the DST to model uncertainty, combine evidence, and provide nuanced measures of belief and plausibility, forming the foundation for its applications in reasoning and decision-making under uncertainty. As an example, we can add another BPA based on the blood pressure of an individual. Table 2 shows a possible mass assignment distribution for the fact that an individual has high blood pressure. This can be provided by the same or another expert.

BPA for individuals having high blood pressure	
Mass for outcome A (high)	0.6
Mass for outcome B (low)	0.2
Uncertainty (A or B)	0.2

Table 2: Example of mass assignment for assessing the possibility of having a heart attack based on the fact of having a high blood pressure

According to the DST, in order to assess the possibilities of a person with high pressure and cholesterol > 250 we can combine both tables using the DS-combination rule which is shown in table 3.

BPA for individuals having high blood pressure and cholesterol level > 250 at the same time	
Mass for outcome A (high)	0.658
Mass for outcome B (low)	0.219
Uncertainty (A or B)	0.121

Table 3: Example of mass assignment for assessing the risk of having a heart attack based on the fact of having a high blood pressure

3.2 DSGD: a DST-based Classifier

The DSGD is a model based on the principles of the DST to perform classification tasks. It works for tabular datasets, assuming that a sample is represented by values in a feature vector. For example, for assessing the overall risk of an individual of having a stroke we characterize each individual by their level of cholesterol, blood pressure, age and smoking habits.

While in the DST the Mass Assignment Functions (MAFs) tables are supposed to be provided by experts, the DSGD model can also generate them automatically from a set of training data, allowing to combine both approaches. The classifier operates in two distinct phases: training and inference. During training, the model learns a set of decision rules from the data, and during inference, it applies these rules to classify new samples based on belief mass functions.

The training process begins with the discretization of continuous attributes. This is achieved by dividing each continuous variable X into statistically meaningful ranges using its mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ), obtaining these values from the training data. A typical (and default) partition used by the model would be defining three ranges such as $X \leq \mu - \sigma$, $\mu - \sigma < X \leq \mu + \sigma$ and $X > \mu + \sigma$, allowing the model to reason over intervals instead of raw continuous values. Categorical attributes (like smoking yes-no) are converted to numerical by giving each category a number and then treated the same way.

Once these partitions are established, initial belief mass functions are assigned to each interval using frequency information from the training data. These masses represent the degree of belief assigned to each class and the level of uncertainty. To optimize classification performance, the mass values are updated during training using gradient-based optimization techniques. This involves computing the gradient of a loss function with respect to each mass value and applying a learning rate to refine the values iteratively. A projection step is used to ensure that each updated mass remains a valid belief assignment within the Dempster-Shafer framework.

The result of this training process is a set of human-readable rules, each mapping a specific attribute range to class-specific belief masses and an associated uncertainty. For example, one set of optimized rules for a single attribute might look as shown in table 4.

These rules capture the model's interpretation of how the input attribute contributes to class membership, including its uncertainty in regions with low predictive power. During the classification of a new sample, the model evaluates the input feature vector against all stored rules. Only the rules whose conditions match the sample's feature values are selected. The associated mass functions of these matching rules are then

combined using Dempster's rule of combination, which aggregates multiple sources of evidence into a single joint belief function. From this fused evidence, belief values are calculated for each possible class. The model then selects the class with the highest belief as the predicted outcome.

Rule Condition	Mass A (high)	Mass (low)	Uncertainty
$X \leq 150$	0.1	0.7	0.2
$150 < X \leq 220$	0.2	0.4	0.4
$X > 220$	0.4	0.3	0.3

Table 4: Example of mass assignment for assessing the possibility of having a heart attack based on the cholesterol level X

A major strength of this approach lies in its interpretability. Each rule is transparent and understandable, allowing domain experts to verify or modify them if needed. The explicit representation of uncertainty also helps identify cases where the model lacks confidence in its prediction, signaling the need for further review or additional data. For example, a medical expert using this classifier might interpret a rule such as "if blood pressure is high, assign 70% belief to the presence of disease," and after examining real patient data, refine the rule further, thereby increasing both the reliability and transparency of the model.

3.3 The DS Clustering Algorithm

The proposed algorithm, which will be called DS Clustering from now on, operates in two main stages, Figure 1 shows the general process of the algorithm. The DS Clustering takes the data of the samples which are going to be clustered and some information given by the user in order to set (meta)parameters for the label selection and the classification stages. The first method applied is the label selection, which determines the clusters. Each cluster is considered a class and given a name, with which the samples of the input data are labelled. Using this label as a class the samples belong to, an interpretable classifier capable of generating rules which define the classes is trained. In this way, we obtain the rules which describe why a certain sample belongs to a certain cluster based only on the attributes of the sample.

In this work, for the clustering process we let the model choose among three well known different clustering methods based on criteria previously given by the user as input. For the clusters' rule generation, we could also have given the flexibility of using among different rule-based interpretable classifiers, but we decided to adopt the DS Classifier given its reliability and the simplicity of the generated rules (see section 4 for this justification).

The first stage, called Label Selection, focuses on identifying clusters in the data by applying three popular clustering algorithms: K-means, DBSCAN, and Agglomerative. K-means is an efficient and simple algorithm that assigns data points to the nearest clusters based on a distance metric. DBSCAN is robust to outliers and capable of detecting clusters of arbitrary shapes. Agglomerative clustering generates a hierarchical view of the data, grouping samples sequentially, thus providing a more

flexible and detailed structure. Figure 2 shows a detailed schema about the process that takes place during the Label Selection stage.

Figure 1: General DS Clustering diagram: the training data and user defined setting of parameters are used as input. The first step is the label selection which defines the clusters

Once these algorithms generate the groupings, labels are assigned to the samples based on a user-defined assignment policy. Options include the **most voted label**, which is the label most frequently assigned by the three algorithms, or the **best label**, determined by the algorithm with the highest silhouette score. For example, if a sample is labeled as 0 by K-Means, cluster 0 by Agglomerative, and cluster 1 by DBSCAN, then under most voted policy, it will be assigned to cluster 0. Additionally, the **number of clusters** is an adjustable parameter in this stage, used to guide the algorithms in creating meaningful groupings within the data. Therefore, in addition to the data to be grouped, the number of clusters is a key parameter in this stage, and it can be adjusted according to the user's needs. This parameter can be determined using traditional methods, such as the elbow method, as well as through interpretability-based criteria, by evaluating which partition allows for a clearer and more coherent characterization of the clusters. The number of clusters to identify is used to guide the clustering algorithms in creating meaningful groups within the data.

The second stage of the algorithm focuses on training the DSGD, which uses the labeled data from the previous stage to provide interpretability to the clustering process. The DSGD is based on the DST and generates a model capable of classifying new samples and explaining the decisions made through interpretable rules. These rules outline the criteria under which a sample is assigned to a specific cluster, improving the transparency of the process. Figure 3 shows in detail a schema for the process of generating rules using the DSGD.

Figure 2: Detailed Label Selection Diagram

The training process includes creating the model using the labeled data, generating categorical rules that define how instances will be classified based on their characteristics, adjusting the model to improve the accuracy of these rules, and predicting the class of new samples. The classifier also provides both the assigned labels and the rules used to determine the cluster membership of each sample.

Figure 3: Detailed DSClassifier usage diagram for generating rules for the clusters

The interpretation of the rules is a crucial component in the design of the algorithm, as it allows users to understand how and why a sample has been assigned to a specific cluster. This offers a significant advantage over traditional clustering methods, which often lack clear explanations of the assignment process.

4 Experiments and results

In this section, we will analyze the performance of the model with respect to its ability to discover clusters and its ability to explain why a certain point should belong to a certain cluster.

4.1 Comparative clustering performance

First, we will compare the performance of the proposed model against other popular clustering models in terms of its ability to find “better” clusters. We will compute following metrics for the **KMeans**, **DBSCAN**, **Agglomerative**, **DSClustering** algorithms:

- **Silhouette**: Measures how similar an object is to its own cluster compared to other clusters, ranging from -1 to 1, with higher values indicating better-defined clusters.
- **Rand-index**: Compares similarity between two clusterings by evaluating the ratio of agreements, where a higher score represents more alignment between the clusters.
- **Dunn-index**: Calculates the ratio of the minimum inter-cluster distance to the maximum intra-cluster distance, with higher values indicating well-separated and compact clusters.

For that, we will use classical real [Github, 2025] and synthetic datasets [Ultsch, 20]. The idea behind using synthetic data sets is that we know beforehand what is the “right” solution for the clustering process and we can check for possible deviations. The synthetic datasets are:

- **Gaussian**: Two clusters from normal distributions centred at [1.2, 0.2] and [0.2, 0.9].
- **Atom**: A 3D dataset with two distinct groups, "kernel" and "hull," representing an atom-like structure. Classes are distinct but not linearly separable.
- **Chainlink**: Contains two intertwined tori, representing non-separable clusters in a plane.
- **Target**: Consists of two large classes within a ring and circle, plus four sets of outliers.
- **TwoDiamonds**: Contains two square-shaped clusters positioned to form diamonds.

The real datasets are:

- **Wine**: Consists of physicochemical properties of various wine samples, used for quality assessment and classification.
- **BreastCancer**: Contains medical records for breast cancer patients, used to classify tumors as malignant or benign based on several features.
- **SAHeart**: A dataset on heart disease risk factors from South African patients used to analyze and predict cardiovascular health outcomes.

- **Iris:** A classic dataset for pattern recognition, featuring measurements of iris flowers for species classification.
- **Stroke:** This dataset comprises medical and demographic data for 15,321 individuals, capturing various physical measurements, blood health indicators, and biochemical metrics. It aims to identify health patterns or risk factors, with each row representing an individual and the `cls` column indicating health outcomes.

Table 5 summarizes the key characteristics of each database in terms of the number or records, the features and the known number of clusters.

Dataset	Records	Features	Know number of clusters
Gaussian	500	2	2
Atom	800	3	2
Chainlink	1000	3	2
Target	770	2	2
TwoDiamonds	800	2	2
Wine	697	13	2
BreastCancer	699	9	2
SAHeart	462	9	2
Iris	150	4	3
Stroke	15321	31	2

Table 5: Summary of the key characteristics of the datasets

To obtain representative performance estimates and minimize the influence of random initialization, we conducted 20 independent iterations for each algorithm on every dataset. In each iteration, the algorithm was initialized with a randomly selected starting configuration, and performance was assessed using the designed metrics (Silhouette score, Rand index, and Dunn index). The metric values obtained in each iteration were then aggregated by computing the arithmetic mean for each metric on a per-dataset basis. This procedure is particularly significant for algorithms such as KMeans, which are notably sensitive to initialization.

Table 6 presents the average performance and standard deviation of the clustering algorithms on synthetic datasets. DS clustering achieves a Silhouette score of 0.56, which is comparable to Agglomerative Clustering (0.58) but lower than DBSCAN (0.68). While DBSCAN appears to produce the most well-separated clusters in synthetic datasets, its Rand index (0.41) is the lowest, suggesting inconsistent cluster labeling compared to ground truth partitions. In contrast, DS clustering achieves a Rand index of 0.51, surpassing both DBSCAN and K-Means, which indicates a more stable and accurate assignment of data points. The Dunn index (0.43) for DS clustering is also the highest among the methods, suggesting that DS clustering maintains better inter-cluster separation and compactness.

Algorithm	Silhouette	Dunn	Rand
KMeans	(0.50, 0.40)	(0.34, 0.35)	(0.49, 0.39)
DBSCAN	(0.68, 0.38)	(0.41, 0.37)	(0.41, 0.46)
Agglomerative	(0.58, 0.39)	(0.36, 0.36)	(0.53, 0.44)
DSClustering	(0.56, 0.46)	(0.43, 0.40)	(0.51, 0.41)

Table 6: Average performance and standard deviation of the clustering methods on all synthetic databases

Table 7 provides a comparison of clustering performance on real-world datasets, where DSClustering demonstrates a notable improvement in clustering validity and interpretability over traditional methods. DSClustering achieves a Silhouette score of 0.74, significantly outperforming K-Means (0.48), DBSCAN (0.48), and Agglomerative Clustering (0.51). This suggests that DSClustering forms more coherent clusters with well-separated boundaries in real-world applications. The Rand index of 0.58 is the highest among all methods, confirming that DSClustering produces the most consistent and meaningful clusters when compared to other techniques. However, DSClustering’s Dunn index (0.27) is slightly lower than that of DBSCAN (0.43) and Agglomerative Clustering (0.41), indicating that while DSClustering ensures meaningful partitions, it may be less sensitive to small intra-cluster variations.

Algorithm	Silhouette	Dunn	Rand
KMeans	(0.48, 0.36)	(0.28, 0.39)	(0.45, 0.37)
DBSCAN	(0.48, 0.33)	(0.43, 0.36)	(0.51, 0.45)
Agglomerative	(0.51, 0.36)	(0.41, 0.39)	(0.54, 0.43)
DSClustering	(0.74, 0.38)	(0.27, 0.38)	(0.58, 0.38)

Table 7: Average performance and standard deviation of the clustering methods on all real databases

Algorithm	Silhouette	Dunn	Rand
KMeans	(0.49, 0.31)	(0.22, 0.29)	(0.45, 0.34)
DBSCAN	(0.68, 0.28)	(0.28, 0.30)	(0.36, 0.38)
Agglomerative	(0.53, 0.29)	(0.29, 0.29)	(0.50, 0.41)
DSClustering	(0.68, 0.35)	(0.33, 0.39)	(0.52, 0.39)

Table 8: Average performance and standard deviation of the clustering methods on all databases

Table 8 aggregates results across both synthetic and real datasets, offering a more comprehensive evaluation of clustering performance. DSClustering achieves a Silhouette score of 0.68, which matches DBSCAN but surpasses Agglomerative Clustering (0.53) and K-Means (0.49). The Dunn index of 0.33 is higher than both K-Means (0.22) and DBSCAN (0.28), further confirming that DSClustering maintains a reasonable balance between compactness and separation. The Rand index (0.52)

outperforms both DBSCAN (0.36) and K-Means (0.45), while closely matching Agglomerative Clustering (0.50). This indicates that DS clustering provides greater stability and consistency in cluster assignments.

The results demonstrate that DS clustering offers a strong alternative to traditional clustering methods, particularly in real-world scenarios where both accuracy and explainability are required. The method's ability to achieve higher Silhouette score and Rand index indicates that it produces more reliable and well-defined clusters while preserving interpretability through rule-based decision-making.

However, there are some trade-offs. While DS clustering excels in real-world datasets, its Dunn index performance suggests that it may struggle with extreme intra-cluster variations. Additionally, compared to DBSCAN, which performs well on synthetic datasets, DS clustering may not always be the best choice for datasets with arbitrarily shaped clusters or those requiring density-based clustering techniques. Nonetheless, DS clustering consistently outperforms K-Means and Agglomerative Clustering, particularly in Rand index, making it a viable solution for interpretable clustering applications.

Overall, the experimental findings confirm that DS clustering successfully integrates clustering validity, achieving competitive clustering quality. The method's effectiveness across diverse datasets suggests that it is well-suited for practical applications where clustering accuracy is essential.

4.2 Comparative interpretability

Model interpretability is key when seeking to understand the clusters that are formed. In particular, clustering methods like K-Means and Agglomerative lack inherent interpretability, so we use an additional classifier to derive comprehensible rules and structures that explain the separation of clusters. To conduct a comprehensive analysis of the interpretability of DS clustering, we will consider the transparency of the model [Strobel, 19], which will refer in this case to the clarity and easiness to understand the reasons behind a sample being assigned to a cluster, thus giving an explanation about the characteristics a cluster has, as a function of the attributes of the samples that belong to it. DS clustering uses the rules generated by the DSGD classifier in order to explain the clusters. We could have used any other interpretable classification model to do this, but the reasons for using DSGD are, in first term the clarity and expressiveness of the generated rules and its accuracy

Decision Trees provide an easily understandable structure, allowing one to follow a set of decisions that lead to a node containing a single class or cluster. This simplicity enables intuitive interpretations, but at the cost of accuracy when working with complex datasets. In these scenarios, improving accuracy requires building deeper trees, which in turn increases the model's complexity and reduces the clarity of decisions, with longer paths or multiple routes leading to the same cluster.

Ripper uses rules that combine features with logical OR and AND operators, making interpretation easier when the number of rules is limited. This approach allows connections between features to be clear and direct, making cluster separation understandable. However, as the number of rules increases, interpretability diminishes. This is because using multiple rules introduces complexity, making the model's understanding less intuitive.

Finally, DS clustering generates rules associated with each cluster that include a mass function and uncertainty, which are used to calculate the importance of each feature. Based on this information, it is possible to rank the rules by importance, allowing for an effective assessment of the most relevant features for each cluster. This approach not only facilitates interpretation but also offers a more comprehensive view of how features are distributed within clusters, taking into account both their weight and the uncertainty in data assignment to groups. To demonstrate the interpretability of these methods, and compare this interpretability with the we analyze two datasets—one synthetic and one real-world dataset (SAHeart)—using the three approaches, that is, given the clusters generated by the first part of the DS clustering model, we will train the three methods and compare the generated set of rules. We will limit the depth of the decision tree to three levels in order to keep the interpretability and avoid overfitting.

Figure 4: Resulting decision tree for the Gaussian distributed data dataset

Gaussian:

Figure 4 shows the decision tree for the clusters generated with the Gaussian-distributed data, it is evident that the clusters can be effectively separated by filtering along the x-axis. The threshold at $x = 0.649$ serves as a crucial dividing point, with most samples being correctly classified. A few misclassified samples can then be refined by incorporating the y-axis for further separation. Broadly, we observe that x plays a key role in cluster differentiation, with one cluster primarily represented by higher x-values and lower y-values, and the other cluster showing the inverse pattern. After applying the first rule, the Gini index decreases significantly to 0.032 and 0.054. This reduction in Gini values underscores the effectiveness of the x-axis threshold in achieving a clean separation between the clusters.

As shown in Table 9, the Ripper algorithm identifies the same rules for the clusters but offers the added advantage of presenting explicit rules that combine both features, providing a clearer understanding of how x and y interact to define the clusters. The rules extracted by Ripper not only highlight the key features but also illustrate their interactions, offering a more interpretable view of how x and y jointly contribute to cluster formation.

Finally, as shown in Table 10, DS-Clustering highlights that x is the most important feature for distinguishing clusters. Moreover, it reveals that as x -values become more extreme, the certainty of the rules increases. This emphasizes the robustness of the clustering process when features exhibit distinct and extreme ranges. The rule with the highest score is R10: $x > 1.042$, indicating a probability of 0.437 of belonging to cluster 1, with an uncertainty (Unc) of 0.563.

C	Rule
0	$[[y \leq -0.056] \vee [0.25 \leq y \leq 0.41] \vee [0.13 \leq y \leq 0.25] \vee [-0.056 \leq y \leq -0.13]] \vee [0.41 \leq y \leq -0.53 \wedge 0.67 \leq x \leq -1.0] \vee [x \geq 1.4] \vee [1.0 \leq x \leq -1.13] \vee [1.13 \leq x \leq -1.26] \vee [1.26 \leq x \leq -1.4] \vee [0.67 \leq x \leq -1.0 \wedge 0.7 \leq y \leq -0.81] \vee [0.67 \leq x \leq -1.0 \wedge 0.53 \leq y \leq -0.7]]$
1	$[[0.1 \leq x \leq 0.25] \vee [-0.057 \leq x \leq 0.1] \vee [x \leq -0.057] \vee [0.25 \leq x \leq 0.42] \vee [0.42 \leq x \leq 0.67 \wedge 0.81 \leq y \leq -0.96] \vee [0.42 \leq x \leq 0.67 \wedge y \geq 1.11] \vee [0.42 \leq x \leq 0.67 \wedge 0.96 \leq y \leq -1.11] \vee [0.42 \leq x \leq 0.67 \wedge 0.53 \leq y \leq -0.7] \vee [0.42 \leq x \leq 0.67 \wedge 0.41 \leq y \leq -0.53] \vee [0.42-0.67 \wedge y=0.7-0.81] \vee [y \geq 1.11] \vee [0.81 \leq y \leq -0.96] \vee [0.96 \leq y \leq -1.11]]$

Table 9: Table with rules generated by Ripper algorithm for the Gaussian distributed data dataset

C	Rule	Score	C1	C2	Unc
0	R10: $x > 1.042$	0.437	0.437	0.000	0.563
	R9: $0.667 < x < 1.042$	0.436	0.436	0.000	0.564
	R11: $y < 0.267$	0.357	0.357	0.000	0.643
	R12: $0.267 < y < 0.549$	0.342	0.334	0.016	0.650
1	R14: $y > 0.831$	0.421	0.000	0.421	0.579
	R7: $x < 0.291$	0.387	0.000	0.387	0.613
	R8: $0.291 < x < 0.667$	0.366	0.000	0.366	0.634
	R13: $0.549 < y < 0.831$	0.273	0.000	0.273	0.727

Table 10: Table with rules generated by the DS-Classifier for the Gaussian distributed data dataset

SAHeart:

Figure 5, shows the decision tree for explaining the clusters that were identified by the first part of the process of the DS-Clustering. We can see that two features emerged as particularly important for classification: systolic blood pressure (SBP) and alcohol consumption. The purple cluster predominantly comprises individuals with high alcohol consumption, highlighting this factor as the main distinguishing characteristic. The green cluster, on the other hand, includes individuals who tend to have high SBP combined with lower alcohol consumption. Additionally, most members of this cluster are over 40 years old. In contrast, the orange cluster represents a more diverse group. It includes individuals with low SBP and low alcohol consumption, regardless of their

age, as well as those with high SBP and low alcohol consumption, provided they are under 40 years old.

As shown in Table 11, Ripper, as a rule-based approach, offered additional insights into the cluster compositions by formulating logical rules. For Cluster 0, high alcohol consumption was the primary factor. Specifically, individuals in this cluster either consumed a very high amount of alcohol (≥ 47.51) or, if their alcohol consumption was moderate (between 27.77 and 47.51), additional factors became relevant. These included type A personality scores (56.0–61.0), moderate tobacco use (2.0–3.44), or moderate obesity levels (21.14–24.8). Cluster 1, in contrast, was defined largely by high SBP, with values equal to or exceeding 166 often co-occurring with a positive family history of cardiovascular disease. For those with slightly lower SBP values (154.0–166.0), other factors such as high obesity (≥ 30.96), moderate LDL cholesterol levels (5.46–6.14), or moderate alcohol consumption (1.39–27.77) played a significant role. Age was also a key determinant, with individuals aged 49–54 frequently appearing in this cluster, alongside some older individuals (over 61 years) with moderate SBP (134.0–138.0). Finally, Cluster 2 consisted of individuals with lower SBP (118.0–138.0) and minimal alcohol consumption (< 1.39). Other contributing factors included low tobacco use (< 0.4), younger age (often under 18), a positive family history of cardiovascular disease, and lower adiposity (< 13.71). This cluster also included some individuals aged 34–45 years with moderate SBP and low LDL cholesterol.

Figure 5: Resulting decision tree for the SAHeart dataset

As shown in Table 12, DS Clustering provided a probabilistic perspective on the interpretability of the clusters, highlighting the most relevant features for each group while considering uncertainty in assignments. In Cluster 0, alcohol consumption was identified as the most important feature, with a rule stating alcohol > 33.738 scoring 0.736. This indicates that high alcohol consumption strongly correlates with

membership in this cluster. Age also played a crucial role, with the rule $age < 32.963$ scoring 0.633, suggesting that younger individuals with high alcohol consumption were likely members of Cluster 0. Other features, such as adiposity and LDL cholesterol, were present but less influential. Cluster 1, in contrast, was dominated by high SBP, as indicated by the rule $SBP > 153.653$ with a score of 0.687. Tobacco consumption emerged as another significant feature, suggesting that members of this cluster tended to have elevated tobacco use. While alcohol consumption also appeared as a feature, it was less critical here (score: 0.498) compared to Cluster 0. This cluster primarily consisted of older individuals with elevated blood pressure and tobacco use, pointing to higher health risks. Cluster 2 was characterized by younger individuals with lower SBP, as reflected in features such as $125.575 < SBP < 139.614$ and $SBP < 125.575$. Age was again an important factor ($age < 32.963$), while adiposity, although present, was less relevant (score: 0.300). This cluster largely represented younger, healthier individuals compared to the other groups. These findings are detailed in Table 7, which summarizes the key features and rules for each cluster.

C	Rule
0	[[alcohol ≥ 47.51] ∨ 27.77 ≤ alcohol ≤ 47.51 ∧ 56.0 ≤ typea ≤ 58.0] ∨ [27.77 ≤ alcohol ≤ 47.51 ∧ ldl=<2.51] ∨ [27.77 ≤ alcohol ≤ 47.51 ∧ 58.0 ≤ typea ≤ 61.0 ∧ 2.0 ≤ tobacco ≤ 3.44] ∨ [27.77 ≤ alcohol ≤ 47.51 ∧ 23.63 ≤ obesity ≤ 24.8] ∨ [27.77 ≤ alcohol ≤ 47.51 ∧ 21.14 ≤ obesity ≤ 22.32]]
1	[[sbp ≥ 166.0 ∧ famhist=1] ∨ [154.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 166.0 ∧ obesity ≥ 30.96] ∨ [144.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 154.0 ∧ ldl=5.46-6.14] ∨ [154.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 166.0 ∧ alcohol ≤ 1.39] ∨ [144.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 154.0 ∧ 49.0 ≤ age ≤ 54.0] ∨ [154.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 166.0 ∧ 23.87 ≤ adiposity ≤ 26.12] ∨ [sbp ≥ 166.0 ∧ tobacco ≤ 0.4] ∨ [144.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 154.0 ∧ tobacco ≥ 9.09] ∨ [sbp ≥ 166.0] ∨ [154.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 166.0 ∧ 11.83 ≤ alcohol ≤ 19.3] ∨ [sbp=154.0-166.0 ∧ 19.3 ≤ alcohol ≤ 27.77] ∨ [144.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 154.0 ∧ famhist=0 ∧ 6.14 ≤ ldl ≤ 7.38] ∨ [138.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 144.0 ∧ 30.06 ≤ adiposity ≤ 32.47] ∨ [138.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 144.0 ∧ adiposity ≥ 35.35] ∨ [age ≥ 61.0 ∧ 134.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 138.0] ∨ [51.0 ≤ typea ≤ 53.0 ∧ 138.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 144.0]]
2	[[tobacco ≤ 0.4 ∧ age ≤ 18.0] ∨ [sbp ≤ 118.0] ∨ [126.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 130.0] ∨ [130.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 134.0 ∧ alcohol ≤ 1.39] ∨ [118.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 122.0 ∧ alcohol ≤ 1.39] ∨ [122.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 126.0 ∧ famhist=1] ∨ [134.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 138.0 ∧ typea=53.0-56.0] ∨ [134.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 138.0 ∧ 40.0 ≤ age ≤ 45.0] ∨ [130.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 134.0] ∨ [18.0 ≤ age ≤ 28.0 ∧ 144.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 154.0] ∨ [122.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 126.0 ∧ alcohol ≤ 1.39] ∨ [34.0 ≤ age ≤ 40.0 ∧ famhist=1] ∨ [138.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 144.0 ∧ famhist=0 ∧ 23.63 ≤ obesity ≤ 24.8] ∨ [118.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 122.0] ∨ [122.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 126.0 ∧ ldl=3.54-3.95] ∨ [134.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 138.0 ∧ adiposity ≤ 13.71] ∨ [134.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 138.0 ∧ 5.46 ≤ ldl ≤ 6.14] ∨ [34.0 ≤ age ≤ 40.0 ∧ 26.12 ≤ adiposity ≤ 28.08] ∨ [134.0 ≤ sbp ≤ 138.0 ∧ tobacco ≤ 0.4] ∨ [adiposity ≤ 13.71]]

Table 11: Table with rules generated by Ripper algorithm for the SAHeart dataset

C	Rule	Score	C0	C1	C2	Unc
0	R36: alcohol > 33.738	0.736	0.610	0.279	0.000	0.111
	R37: age < 32.963	0.633	0.498	0.000	0.305	0.197
	R21: 25.593 < adiposity < 30.511	0.589	0.525	0.000	0.137	0.339
	R15: ldl < 3.329	0.462	0.389	0.000	0.158	0.453
	R38: 32.963 < age < 42.734	0.410	0.322	0.000	0.199	0.478
1	R10: sbp > 153.653	0.687	0.161	0.611	0.000	0.228
	R14: tobacco > 6.710	0.512	0.000	0.512	0.000	0.488
	R36: alcohol > 33.738	0.498	0.610	0.279	0.000	0.111
	R40: age > 52.504	0.435	0.000	0.435	0.000	0.565
	R35: 17.480 < alcohol < 33.738	0.397	0.000	0.353	0.094	0.553
2	R37: age < 32.963	0.495	0.498	0.000	0.305	0.197
	R8: 125.575 < sbp < 139.614	0.426	0.000	0.000	0.426	0.574
	R7: sbp < 125.575	0.417	0.011	0.000	0.412	0.578
	R38: 32.963 < age < 42.734	0.322	0.322	0.000	0.199	0.478
	R21: 25.593 < adiposity < 30.511	0.300	0.525	0.000	0.137	0.339

Table 12: Table with rules generated by the DS-Classifier for the SAHeart dataset

4.3 Comparative reliability

To assess the reliability of the rules provided by the interpretable classification models (decision tree, Ripper and Ds.classifier) which govern the assignment of a sample to a specific cluster, we introduce the concept of confidence in interpretability, which quantifies the degree to which a method can justify the assignment of a data point to a particular cluster. This confidence measure is evaluated through the "accuracy" of each method, separately for synthetic and real-world datasets.

Conventionally, classification accuracy is measured by training a model on a subset of the data and evaluating its performance on an unseen test set. However, in the context of clustering, our objective is not to predict new assignments but rather to assess how well a method can explain why a data point, which actively participated in the clustering process, belongs to a specific cluster.

This approach naturally results in high accuracy values, as the evaluation is conducted on data points already involved in clustering. Therefore, rather than focusing on the absolute proximity of accuracy scores to 100%, we emphasize the relative differences between methods, as these provide a more meaningful measure of their explanatory power and, consequently, their confidence in interpretability.

The results presented in the Table 10 indicate that DSclustering consistently achieves the highest mean accuracy across both synthetic (99.3%) and real datasets (97.6%), suggesting that it provides the most reliable and interpretable clustering explanations among the evaluated methods. Ripper follows closely, with accuracy values of 98.4% and 95.9% for synthetic and real datasets, respectively, demonstrating strong performance but slightly lower confidence in interpretability compared to DSclustering. Decision Tree, while still achieving high accuracy, exhibits the lowest values (93.6% for synthetic and 92.1% for real datasets), suggesting that its interpretability-based confidence is more affected by the nature of the dataset. Notably, all methods exhibit a slight decrease in accuracy when applied to real-world data, which

is expected due to increased complexity and potential noise. However, the relative ranking among methods remains consistent, reinforcing the robustness of DSCLustering in providing explanatory power. These findings highlight the importance of selecting rule-based models that maximize interpretability while maintaining high fidelity to the clustering assignments.

Method	Synthetic Datasets	Real Datasets
Decision Tree	0.936	0.921
Ripper	0.984	0.959
DSCLustering	0.993	0.976

Table 10: Reliability measured as the accuracy of the interpretable rule-based classification methods used

5 Conclusions

This study introduced DSCLustering, an innovative approach that integrates Dempster-Shafer Theory with clustering methodologies to enhance both validity and interpretability. Traditional clustering techniques, such as K-Means, DBSCAN, and Agglomerative Clustering, often focus on maximizing compactness and separation but lack an intrinsic explanation for their assignments. DSCLustering bridges this gap by leveraging belief mass functions to provide confidence scores for cluster assignments, enabling a structured and transparent decision-making process.

The experimental results demonstrate that DSCLustering not only achieves competitive clustering performance but also excels in interpretability. Unlike alternative rule-based classifiers like RIPPER, which generate a large number of interdependent rules that can become difficult to interpret, DSCLustering produces a concise, structured, and confidence-weighted set of rules. Each cluster is characterized by a ranked set of rules with associated belief values, allowing users to understand the most influential factors in determining cluster membership. The confidence measure introduced in this work quantifies the reliability of these interpretability rules, showing that DSCLustering achieves the highest confidence in rule-based explanations among tested methods. Furthermore, the clarity and conciseness of DSGD-generated rules make DSCLustering highly interpretable while maintaining robust classification accuracy. This is particularly beneficial in high-stakes applications such as healthcare, finance, and customer analytics, where both trust and transparency are crucial. The ability to quantify uncertainty and rank the importance of rules sets DSCLustering apart from existing approaches, offering a more nuanced and reliable framework for understanding clustering results. By combining robust clustering performance with confidence-weighted interpretability, DSCLustering represents a significant step forward in the development of transparent machine learning models. This work highlights the growing need for clustering techniques that provide both accuracy and clear decision-making explanations, encouraging further research in interpretable unsupervised learning.

While DSCLustering has demonstrated its effectiveness in combining high interpretability with confidence-weighted clustering, several avenues for future research remain open. One promising direction is the extension of DSCLustering to dynamic or streaming data, allowing for real-time updates to belief masses and rule-based cluster descriptions as new data arrives. This would be particularly useful in real-time analytics and adaptive decision-making applications, such as fraud detection or evolving customer segmentation. Another area of exploration is the integration of additional uncertainty quantification techniques beyond Dempster-Shafer Theory, such as fuzzy logic or Bayesian inference, to enhance the robustness of confidence measurements. This could help refine rule selection and improve adaptability in cases where data is highly noisy or partially missing. Additionally, future work could focus on optimizing rule generation in high-dimensional spaces. While DSGD already produces concise and interpretable rule sets, further improvements could involve dimensionality reduction techniques or hybrid clustering-classification models that balance simplicity with discriminative power. Finally, applying DSCLustering to diverse real-world datasets across multiple domains, such as medical diagnosis, explainable finance models, and legal decision support systems, would further validate its practical utility. Extending the method to multi-label and hierarchical clustering scenarios could also broaden its applicability in complex decision-making environments. By addressing these directions, DSCLustering can evolve into a more generalized and adaptive framework for interpretable and confidence-aware clustering, advancing the field of explainable unsupervised learning.

Despite the strengths of DSCLustering, certain limitations should be acknowledged. One potential weakness lies in the computational complexity of the Dempster-Shafer-based rule generation, particularly when applied to large-scale, high-dimensional datasets. Since the belief mass functions require multiple levels of evidence aggregation, the approach may not scale efficiently without further optimization. Additionally, the dependency on well-calibrated mass function assignments could introduce sensitivity to noisy or biased data, potentially affecting rule quality and confidence estimates. Another limitation is that DSCLustering assumes that well-defined and separable structures exist within the data, which may not always hold true in complex, overlapping, or highly nonlinear distributions. Furthermore, while the method significantly improves interpretability compared to traditional clustering techniques, the need for expert validation of generated rules remains crucial, as automatic rule extraction does not always capture domain-specific nuances. Addressing these limitations, in future research could further enhance the robustness, scalability, and applicability of DSCLustering across diverse domains.

Finally, we believe that users can greatly benefit from a clustering model that produces clear and simple rules defining each cluster, as it transforms what is typically a black-box grouping process into a transparent and interpretable outcome. Instead of merely assigning data points to clusters without explanation, the model articulates which specific ranges or combinations of variable values—derived from the embedding vector—characterize membership in each cluster. This allows users to understand the underlying structure of the data, recognize patterns, and validate or challenge the grouping based on domain knowledge. Such rule-based clusters empower decision-makers to translate unsupervised learning into actionable insights, enabling them to label, monitor, and even intervene in complex systems with confidence and clarity.

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